

THE ROLE OF DEFINITIONS IN THE “CANON OF MEDICAL SCIENCE”

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13956686>

Abstract. *Two decades of the 21st century is characterized by increased globalization and increased scientific and technological progress of human civilization, along with the exacerbation of many problems, including the coronavirus pandemic, which has changed the lives of all states and all people on the planet. In this regard, the problem of rethinking our attitude to health, methods of treatment, and disease prevention has become particularly acute. These issues directly decide the future prospects for the survival of humanity and the relationship with its environment. In this regard, the philosophical understanding of the scientific and medical creativity of Abu Ali ibn Sino, who created the most complete systematized teaching in the Middle Ages, which has not lost its significance for modern medicine, acquires particular relevance.*

Keywords: *logic, philosophy, Abu Ali ibn Sina, revival, medicine, methodology, knowledge of the world.*

Introduction. Abu Ali Ibn Sino lived and worked in the era of the Eastern Renaissance – the era of the Revival of ancient Eastern, ancient Greek and Roman spiritual culture, the era that gave birth to such a brilliant galaxy of figures in philosophy, culture, science and poetry as Al-Kindi, Al-Ghazali, Abu Abdullah Rudaki, Abulkasim Firdousi, Abu Bakr Zakariya ar-Razi, Muhammad Ismail Bukhori, At-Termizi, Al-Khwarizmi, Abu Nasr Farabi and Abu Rayhan Beruni and many others. It was a period of economic growth and cultural flourishing, especially in such cities as Bukhara, Samarkand, Nishapur, Gurgenj, Isfahan, Hamadan, Rey, which became the centers of economy and culture in the East. In particular, Bukhara was the capital of the Samanid state and a major center of trade with India, China, Syria, Iraq, Russia and other countries of the East and West.

This contributed to the development of trade and crafts, the flourishing of crafts led to the emergence of large corporations of artisans, to the spread of commodity-money relations. The largest library in the East of that time, known as "Savon al-hikmat" (Repository of Wisdom), was collected in Bukhara. The centers of cultural and scientific thought became the "Societies of the Enlightened" ("Majlisi Ulamo") and special "Houses of Science" ("Dorilfunun"), which functioned in Bukhara, Khorezm, Samarkand.

Material and Methods. The article is based on a detailed analysis of the logical teachings of Abu Ali ibn Sina and the content of the “Canon of Medicine” to prove the systematicity, completeness, success and significance of the main medical work which were largely determined not only by the many years of successful activity of the practicing physician, but also by a strictly logical approach to its presentation.

Literature analysis. When writing this article, a wide range of philosophical, logical, historical, medical literature was used; the sources were based on numerous scientific works by famous scientists: V.V. Bartold, I.M. Muminov, M.M. Khayrullaev, M.N. Boltaev, V. Zakhidov, T.I. Rainov, M.N. Vasiliev, M.S. Burabaev, A.V. Sagadeev, M.N. Sayfullaev, S. Akkelman, J. Guinness and others. A great contribution to understanding the significance of the logical teachings

of Ibn Sina was made by associate professors of the Department of Philosophy and Logic of the National University of Uzbekistan, D.E. Fayzikhodjaeva and O.I. Stepanova. In general, the degree of study of the work of Abu Ali ibn Sina is quite high, but a separate work devoted to the logical foundations of "Canon of Medicine" has not been written.

Research results. Modern logic does not have a single theory of definition, but despite all the differences in approaches and interpretations, it is possible to identify a fundamental core. Its essence lies in the fact that a formally correct, clearly and correctly formulated definition is the only way to prevent misunderstandings both in scientific research and in the business field, in everyday disputes. It is always necessary to clearly understand what is meant by the concepts used.

Since definitions reveal the essential characteristics of objects, they become absolutely indispensable in the process of cognition at any stage. The importance of this logical procedure was pointed out by all philosophers - from Aristotle, Al-Farabi, D. Locke, F. Bacon, T. Hobbes, I. Kant to modern researchers - B. Russell, Morris R. Cohen, E. Nagel, D. P. Gorsky, A. D. Getmanova, Yu. V. Ivlev, A. A. Ivin, V. I. Kirillov, I. V. Khomenko, famous Uzbek logicians - academician M. M. Khairullaev, M. Sh. Sharipov, D. E. Fayzikhodzhaeva and many others. With all the diversity and different interpretations of modern logic, all textbooks on formal logic necessarily have a chapter devoted to definitions.

Without a clearly formulated definition of the concepts used, it is useless to start any discussion: political, economic, and even every day. Therefore, in the logical teachings of Abu Ali ibn Sina, special attention is paid to this problem. The great doctor insists on the position that medical science cannot exist in principle without clearly formulated definitions of the body, all organs and organ systems, diseases and ailments, causes of diseases, drugs and medicines, methods of treating diseases. He notes that the same medical term can be defined differently depending on the specific situation. Everything depends on what goals you are pursuing, what exactly you want to pay attention to first of all, for whom the definition is intended. Therefore, there are many types of definitions from which you can easily choose what suits you best in a particular case.

Modern logical theory connects a sign (word) with its specific meaning, and since the meaning is the link between the sign and the content, then by defining the meaning, we thereby define the content. The main goal of definitions is the standardization of language usage; it appears in any case when there is a need to clarify the meaning of a term, to explicate, to explain its meaning. Since the use of words is constantly changing, there is no need to consider a definition as something permanent, given once and for all. Therefore, in logic, it is customary to say that definitions are conventional, that is, they are the subject of an agreement on the use of a particular word. Such an agreement can be long-term and stable if we are talking about all speakers of Russian, Uzbek and other languages, but it can also be an agreement between you and your interlocutor within the framework of a specific dialogue. In scientific research based on precise definitions, there is a constant need to give new definitions due to the discovery of new facts that clarify the nature of various processes and phenomena. So, the most frequently encountered and used expression is: "the definition of a concept is a logical operation that reveals the content of the concept, that is, the listing of those essential and distinctive features of objects, processes and phenomena that are reflected in thinking" [1, p. 658].

Since only the most important, essential characteristics are reflected in the definition, as a rule, definitions are concise and laconic. This is the advantage of the definition as a logical operation and allows you to easily remember them and operate with them in the process of

cognition. No science, no textbook can do without definitions. This is what the famous scientific methodologist K. Popper says in his famous work "Logic and the Growth of Scientific Knowledge" [2, p.782], so the definition is understood as a logical approach that allows:

There are different types of definitions: nominal and real, explicit and implicit, genetic and by purpose; the most common is the definition by genus and species difference [3.p.164]. The question of the effectiveness of certain types of definitions is actively discussed in the scientific literature [4.p.223].

What types of definitions did Abu Ali ibn Sina use? Aristotle also introduced the distinction between real and nominal definitions, through genus and species difference. As it is known, generic definitions are traditionally called the most common and classical type of definitions. They are constructed by indicating the genus and specific difference. The generic concept shows what class of objects the defined thing belongs to, and the specific difference shows how the defined thing differs from other objects of the same class. Thus, the "Canon of Medicine", namely the first section, opens with a definition of medicine through a genus and specific difference: "Medicine is a science that cognizes the state of the human body as it is healthy or has lost health, in order to maintain health and restore it if it is lost" [5.p.264]. Here we see a classical generic-specific definition. "Medicine" is the defined thing; "science" is a generic concept; "cognizing the state of the human body as it is healthy or has lost health, in order to maintain health and restore it if it is lost" - a complex specific difference.

Ibn Sina uses similar generic and specific definitions when analyzing the organs of the human body. For example, "The thoracic vertebrae are those vertebrae to which the ribs adjoin, surrounding the respiratory organs" [6.p.499]. Similar definitions are found in the anatomy of muscles, bones, veins and arteries, internal organs, etc. This type of definition is also actively used in the study of drugs and medicines. For example, "A rarefied medicine is a medicine that is characterized by being divided into tiny particles in the body under the influence of our natural force" [7.p.198].

Further: such are, for example, saffron and Chinese cinnamon. As a rule, Ibn Sina's definitions are accompanied by numerous examples explaining the definitions. Similar definitions are given for other types of medicines - dense, viscous, absorbent, thinning, dissolving, cleansing and many others.

Thus, we see that the generic concept shows the set (class) to which the defined thing belongs (for example, it is a medicine), and the specific difference shows how it differs from other objects of the same set (from other medicines). This type of definition is the most complete, convenient and therefore widely used by the great healer not only in the "Canon of Medical Science", but also in his other works on medicine. Following Ibn Sina, this type of definition is widely used in subsequent centuries.

Ibn Sina often uses so-called enumerative definitions. In such definitions, the defining part is a simple listing of objects that fall under the definition. Such definitions can be convenient when a word denotes a small number of elements that can be easily listed. Such a definition is used when considering "nature" as the basis of processes occurring in the body. Based on the definitions of primary elements and depending on them (heat, coldness, humidity and dryness), Ibn Sina distinguishes eight types of nature. Thus, Ibn Sina shows that specific treatment must be selected for each nature. What suits "sluggish" natures will not suit "hot" natures. Thus, this type of definition is one of the grounds for choosing appropriate medications, diet, care, which subsequently contributes to effective treatment and recovery of the patient. Thus, we want to show that the logical foundations of the "Canon of Medical Science" were the instrument by which Ibn Sina's main medical work was not only systematically and meaningfully constructed, but also contributed to more effective treatment, and therefore, to the recovery of patients.

In scientific literature it is generally accepted that Ibn Sina did not use definitions for their intended purpose. We believe that he used definitions for their intended purpose, which we will try to illustrate below.

Very often Abu Ali ibn Sina uses definitions by purpose (sometimes they are called target).

Thus, in the first chapter in thirteen paragraphs "On bones" he says: "We affirm: among the bones there are those that perform the role of a foundation in relation to the body, and on them the body is built. Such, for example, are the vertebrae of the spinal column. It is the foundation for the body, on which the body is built, as a ship is built on a beam, which is laid first. And some bones perform the purpose of armor and a protector in relation to the body, for example, the parietal bone, while others serve as a weapon that reflects shocks and damage" [8.p.588].

Thus, Ibn Sina, when describing medicinal plants, has numerous uses of the definition by purpose. "Anise - opens blockages, slightly astringent, soothes pain, drives away sweat, ... dissolves winds ... soothes headaches, facilitates breathing and increases milk secretion, helps with blockages of the liver and spleen ..., increases the secretion of urine and leucorrhoea, cleanses the uterus from liquid white discharge, encourages intercourse ..., opens blockages in the kidneys ..." [9.p. 396].

Similar definitions by purpose are given to many other medicinal herbs: wormwood, myrtle, Arabian acacia, sea onion, bitter melon, coriander, fragrant rush, juniper berries, lichens, chamomile, fragrant marigolds, dodder, lavender, nutmeg and walnuts and a thousand other medicinal plants.

Discussion. The widespread use of medicinal herbs contributed to the selection of an effective method of treating the disease and minimized the side effects on the body from their use. We believe that this is the positive experience of the medicine of the Great Healer, which must be used in modern medical practice, since drugs in the 20th - 21st centuries have side effects, which we are all well aware of.

Ibn Sina also widely uses such a technique as comparison. For example, paragraph three of the first article of the first volume of the "Canon of Medical Science" is called "On the knowledge of the nature of simple medicines by comparison."

As it is known, genetic definition as a separate type of definition was introduced in the New Age by the scientist Thomas Hobbes. The term "genetic definition" comes from the Greek word genesis - origin, source. Genetic is a definition that indicates the origin of an object, the way it was formed. Modern textbooks show that by revealing the way an object was formed, its origin,

genetic definition plays an important cognitive role. As a type of definition through genus and species is different, it has the same logical structure and is subject to the same rules. In scientific sources devoted to the work of Ibn Sina, the opinion was established that Avicenna did not use this type of definition. Indeed, it was not singled out by scientists as a separate type of definition, but it is relatively rarely present in the "Canon of Medical Science".

Thus, much attention is paid to the driving forces, the causes (that is, the origin) of various diseases. In particular, he writes: "As for the driving force, it is the force that stretches the tendons and weakens them; it moves the organs and joints, releasing and retracting them. The passage for this force is in the nerves adjacent to the muscles. This kind of force is divided (into categories) according to the categories of the sources of movement, so that in each muscle there is a driving force of another nature, which follows the greatness of the mind, causing the volitional impulse" [10.p.247].

Conclusions. The Canon of Medicine by Abu Ali ibn Sina shows that his approach to studying human health and identifying the causes of diseases is based on a systemic study that combines theoretical sources, accumulation of practical observations and their logical processing. The substantive point of Abu Ali ibn Sina's teaching is the approach to analyzing the causes of diseases as a complex systemic psychosomatic phenomenon. Modern medicine shares this opinion. In addition, Ibn Sina is of the opinion that a number of diseases are multi-causal, multi-factorial, and, as a result, multi-symptom, complex. Therefore, it is very important to identify the logical connection between the external manifestations of the disease - symptoms and internal causes, between numerous external factors and internal processes occurring in all organs and organ systems.

In conclusion, we note that the study and analysis of the essence and sources, branches of the norms of Islamic law on the basis of the modern concept of the family, allows us to clarify which rights and freedoms are universal and which are derived from the standpoint of traditions, culture, religion and customs of a particular society. This study reveals the influence of traditions and customs on the process of protecting family relations at the national and regional levels. It is also worth noting that the success of democratic reforms largely depends on the happy and prosperous life of the family in society. Therefore, it is necessary to determine the factors of all spheres of public life that affect the activity of family members, take into account the general social and national-religious characteristics in developing theoretical conclusions and practical suggestions.

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